

THE ROLE OF INTERNET IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6571497>

N.Abdiganiyeva

Student

Karakalpak State University after named Berdakh, Uzbekistan

Annotation: *This article discusses the role of the Internet in education, that is, how we can use IT to teach a foreign language, and how to increase students' speaking skills through various videos.*

Key words: *World, science, technology, development, innovative, pedagogical, requirements, foreign languages.*

In today's fast-paced world, science and technology are also growing rapidly. Development in every field is moving forward. In particular, great changes are taking place in science. Delivering each subject to students using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education. Especially after the adoption of the Resolution of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abduganievich Karimov dated December 13, 2012 No. PP 1875, the attention to teaching and learning foreign languages in our country has increased. A new stage, a new era in the teaching of foreign languages has begun in our country. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communication and media is required in the process of teaching foreign languages. New methods and requirements for teaching foreign languages in the country have been developed in accordance with the Recommendations of the European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to him, textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The demand for learning a foreign language is growing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking), each of which provides specific concepts and skills.

Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of foreign language learning (reading, writing,

listening comprehension and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. The use of modern technologies in the educational process is also an important factor for students to be familiar with and use information and communication technologies. One of the most effective ways is to teach and learn a foreign language using modern technology. In this process, including:

- When using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language;
- It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs;
- use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods;
- CD players are available. The use of these tools will make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. In the process of globalization, it is hard to imagine our lives without the internet. It is one of the most effective ways to learn and use a foreign language. You will be able to communicate with foreign speakers through the Internet. Writing exercises can be improved by writing a letter via e-mail.

The use of graphic organizers in the educational process is one of the most important visits in the coverage of the topic and its delivery to students. It is also possible to use several different graphic organizers to illuminate a topic. When teaching a foreign language, it is advisable to use graphic organizers to explain new words and grammatical rules. These are also easy to remember when given by graphic organizers. The use of different tables in the process of teaching a foreign language is also very effective. Using tables in the learning process, students can follow a specific grammatical rule, such as composing sentences using tenses and placing new words. At a time when the need for learning a foreign language is high, the effective use of modern information technologies, innovative educational technologies in the educational process makes this process more effective. The effectiveness of innovative educational technologies lies in their correct and effective use in the educational process.

Information technology or IT (from English "information technology", IT) represents a wide range of sciences and activities related to the use of data management and processing technologies, including computer technology. IT deals with the use of computers and software to store, modify, process, transmit and receive information. According to the definition adopted by UNESCO, "information technology is an interconnected set of scientific, technological, and engineering sciences that explores ways to effectively organize the work of those involved in the processing and storage of information; computational technology and methods of organization and interaction of people and production equipment, their practical application, as well as relevant social,

economic and cultural problems. Information technology requires complex training, high cost and high technology, they are based and mainly depend on technical, software, information, methodological and organizational software, and software is used to collect, process, analyze information. performs storage and retrieval functions.

Thus, by teaching a foreign language using the Internet, both teachers and students will have better opportunities in their work, so the introduction of ICT in the teaching process is a topical issue. The effectiveness of modern lessons is achieved through educational programs, the search for information on the Internet, as a result, the growth of interest in learning foreign languages, understanding of the relevance of international and intercultural communication, expanding the scope of the educational environment.